

PHILOLOGICAL ISSUES IN THE EYES OF YOUNG SCIENTISTS

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As you know, one of the problems is the problem of harmonizing two trends: the preservation of classical university education, especially philological education, and the adaptation of educational activities to the demands of the labor market. This problem attracts the attention of researchers from different countries.

In developed Western European countries, this problem is solved successfully. The preservation of classical philological education will not happen by itself, fundamental philological education is doomed to failure under "natural selection" in the world of market competition, and it needs to be protected. Indeed, on the one hand, national self-identification occurs through language. On the other hand, language is one of the main means of influencing all spheres of society. The role of language in the life of humankind today has grown so much that there is a sharp struggle for the authority of this or that language and culture in the world, significant forces and means are spent on this. The teaching of the Uzbek language cannot be equated with the teaching of "profitable" market specialties. What determines a people, civilization, culture in the world of other peoples, civilizations and cultures, what constitutes the spiritual "gene pool", forms a person and a citizen, is, among other things, the native language, native literature, national history. It seems that what has been said is enough to realize the need and justification for close state attention to the prospects of philological education.

Another of the problems of modern philological education is the problem of teaching the culture of reading, which can be briefly formulated in the form of questions "Why read? What to read? How to read? How to evaluate learning outcomes?"

There is an acute problem of understanding Uzbek classical literature by modern Uzbek readers. Most textual information eludes such readers due to ignorance of their native, but historically distant cultural background (and if there is "no information", then it means that reading is not interesting). "There are gaps in cultural consciousness: dozens of names for schoolchildren mean nothing. The common language of culture is "crumbled". Since any text is generated by a certain linguistic culture, one or another historical and social environment, its understanding is impossible without knowledge of the

corresponding presuppositions. This includes the search for reminiscences, intertextual connections, distant, non-standard associations in the interpretation of the text.

The cognitive approach to linguistics involves considering any text not only as a set of proper linguistic (structural-semantic), but also as a system of cognitive, linguistic, cultural, ethno-psychological aspects. Since the language is realized in oral and written texts and exists as a stable structure in the collective consciousness of its speakers, the level of language competence and, accordingly, the general speech culture of each individual is determined by the quantity and quality of the texts read.

Science fiction writer D. Bykov, supporting the idea of compiling a list of literature recommended for extracurricular reading of schoolchildren, focused on the fact that such literature should be both exciting and educational at the same time, but it should also educate: "There are books that irreversibly change a person, that make him evil or good." Moreover, these criteria - artistic, educational and educational value - should be applied to the mandatory list of works for reading, which should include the so-called exemplary (canonical) texts.

Based on the idea that the school should not only provide a certain set of scientific information, but also develop skills for solving real life problems and working independently with information, the international organization Professional International Student Assessment (PISA) has developed and applies tests to assess the skills of high school students work with text information. This skill is called "functional literacy", which "is the object of monitoring the quality of education at school. Reading literacy is reading comprehension, comprehension, the ability to work with information, use it for various purposes. Familiarity with the content of these tests allows us to conclude that they test the purely intellectual abilities of students, and often these are tests of the elementary level of IQ: what is said in the text, where the text indicates that the character intends to do something or was there something, etc.

It is necessary to conduct constant work on the search for the optimal invariant of the content of philological education. The invariant, despite its name, should be developed, supplemented or reduced, taking into account the relevance and precedent of the texts proposed for study. Nevertheless, relevance and precedence still cannot be the exclusive or dominant criteria for the inclusion of new texts in the program or the exclusion of obsolete texts from it. They should be taken into account in the complex of those criteria that determine the

selection of works for the school or university program because of a value-semantic, educational approach. Texts for reading should be selected according to such indicators as the norms and cultural values presented in them. The selection criteria are the talent of the author, the educational role of the book, the fame of the work, the fact that the literary community recognizes the author (work).

It is necessary to introduce the subject "Culture of reading" as an independent scientific and educational discipline in school and university philological training.

We need a dictionary of concepts specifically for the sphere of philological education, in compiling which it is necessary to take into account the opinion of all categories of participants in the educational process - teachers, scientists, representatives of all branches of government, parents and students, identified through questionnaires, discussions, and scientific research.

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